

EVALUATION OF STICKY TRAPS FOR MONITORING THE POPULATION OF SPITTLEBUGS IN SOUTHERN ITALY

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Estimating the relative abundance and seasonal patterns of adults of *Philaenus spumarius*, the predominant European vector of *Xylella fastidiosa*, is important for implementation of surveillance and control strategies for the diseases caused by the bacterium and currently emerging in Europe. Sweep net or coloured sticky trap are a quick and simple sampling method for monitoring the relative abundance of one or more insect species over a large region. In this work we evaluated sweep net and different coloured sticky traps placed in olive and almond orchards as methods for sampling spittlebugs (i.e. the two vectors *P. spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris*) and other xylem sap feeders occurring in the two crops. In a first field experiment, six different coloured traps (white, red, blue, yellow, yellow with circle-pattern and yellow with line-pattern) (Russel IPM) were screened. Forty and 22 traps/color were placed in olive and almond orchards, respectively, on the southwest side of the trees and left for 1 week. The results of the inspections of these traps indicated that yellow colored traps are more attractive for spittlebugs than the other traps. Among the yellow traps, those with line and circle pattern captured more spittlebugs as well as more planthoppers (i.e. less selective than the plain yellow traps). Subsequently in the same orchards, yellow sticky traps were placed and surveys performed at 2-weeks interval were performed from June to September 2018. Fifty traps were randomly replaced every two weeks and concomitantly the same orchards were monitored by sweep net (20 random sample units/orchard, with 10 sweep net per each sampling unit). The data so far collected indicate that yellow traps are more efficient in capturing of *P. spumarius*. This was particularly evident in the almond orchard, where a peak of 50 specimens/trap/week were recorded, versus peaks of maximum 8 individuals collected by sweep net.

In the site used for our study, characterized by abundant population of spittlebugs, yellow sticky traps resulted the most attractive coloured traps, and surveys using sticky traps were more efficient than sweep net. These indications may be useful to support further studies for dispersal dynamics or evaluation of the efficacy of insecticides applications.